

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING MODAL VERB IN ESL

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Annotation: The article deals with important methods that focus on teaching modal verbs in ESL classes. Moreover, examples of some productive games that help to organize interesting and resulting lesson on the topic were highlighted by author.

Key words: *grammar, abilities, possibilities, time consuming , “Give Me a Sign” , “Agony Aunts” , “Fortune Tellers” , “Guess the Job”.*

In today's process of globalization, the effect of the radical reform of the education system of Uzbekistan is evident in all areas related to this area. The state pays special attention to the teaching and further development of foreign languages in the education system, which is a key sector of socio-economic, political and cultural life of the country. At a video conference chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on May 6, 2021 on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, the problems in the system were analyzed in detail and priorities were identified. On this basis, the issue of attitudes to foreign language teaching is addressed in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 No PP-5117 "On measures to bring the promotion of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level": "... education in foreign languages It is no coincidence that the need to develop as a policy priority, radically improve the

quality of education in this area, attract qualified teachers to the field and increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages "[1]. In the process of learning any language grammar plays great role. Because, without knowing grammar one can't improve any skill in that language. English language learners are often confused by modal verbs because they are used differently than other verbs and in a wide variety of situations such as asking for permission and giving advice. There are a couple methods you can use to teach students modal verbs. One is to introduce only a few words at a time and complete several practice activities before attempting to introduce additional vocabulary. Another way you can teach modal verbs is to structure your lessons around their uses. You could leave all the modal verbs written on the board for the whole chapter but use only the ones appropriate for giving advice in one lesson and asking for permission in another for instance.

Start by introducing all the modal verbs you wish to talk about. This may include can, could, may, might, must, will, would, shall, should, and ought to but, depending on the level of your class, you can narrow it down to those you feel are most important. Obviously there are no images that can help students understand the meanings of these words so you can do pronunciation practice simply by pointing to the words on the board. In your introduction you can cover some rules that apply to all modal verbs. Unlike most verbs, no -s is needed to form the third person singular. For example "He should ~." is correct, while "He work." is incorrect. Adding not forms the negative structure. Additionally they always require another verb because they cannot act as the main verb in a sentence and they only have present tense forms so unlike the word swim, there is no past tense form for modals. This may seem like a long and confusing introduction but it is best after the pronunciation practice to simply write the modals and their rules off to the side of the board for reference[2].

Modals are often used to talk about abilities and possibilities or lack of them. Some of the words you want to focus on in this section are can, could, may, and might. Talk to your students about things they can do and practice using can in the target structure because this will be the easiest word to start off with. Next you should talk about might because it is also commonly used when talking about present possibilities such as “We can’t play music in class because the other classes might be taking tests.” which nicely combines the two words in one sentence. Building upon that, talk about how could and may are used to discuss future abilities and possibilities and also how could can be used to talk about the past in a sentence such as “When I was a child, I could climb trees.” So as you can see just this one section on modals can take awhile. It is best to introduce structures gradually and to plan lots of practice activities for each. You can center another lesson on asking for permission or making an offer or request. Can, could, may, shall, will, and would can all be used so you might want to break this up into pairs by introducing can and could, will and would, and finally may and shall. In other lessons you can cover using modals to make suggestions and give advice, to talk about obligations and prohibitions, and lastly cover using ought to and should to say what the correct action would be for instance “She ought to see a doctor.” or “We should be quiet while the teacher is talking.” For some classes it is not necessary to cover all the different uses of modal verbs so feel free to choose what is most important and then cover those items thoroughly before moving on to the next topic.

Modal verb is a verb that cannot work without another verb. These include can, will, must, ought to, may, would, could, should and shall. It can be tricky when attempting to get the message of these particular verbs across to the student, so it is important to plan the class carefully. Always remember that it is important to keep the students engaged. They need to be able to keep focus (since grammar, for the most part, isn’t considered to be fun for most students).

Learning intricate rules can be boring and time consuming for many, so a lot of teachers tend to disregard this method of teaching. Of course, in some cases, it might be easier to explain how something works grammatically and then give an example. There are many possible options available, and it is also important for the teachers themselves to remember that with a little bit of imagination, any activity can be made to serve a purpose[3]. Grammar lessons don't have to be boring or tedious. With these ESL activities, you can make them fun! That way, students will pick up modal verbs more easily. Here are five activities so fun that students will forget they're even learning!

1. Give Me a Sign- This exercise is great for teaching how to use modal verbs for prohibition and obligation. It uses real-life examples that students see around them every day, so they should have no problem picking up the grammar and putting it into context. Start by showing or drawing a picture of a no smoking sign to your class and asking them what it means. If they say "no smoking," ask them to elaborate with a full sentence. This should elicit "you can't smoke," or something to that effect. Then, ask your students how they could make the sentence stronger. This should prompt them to give you "you must not smoke." From here, you can teach a selection of modal verbs, such as "have to," "must" and "mustn't." Create a worksheet or PowerPoint presentation which provides a selection of signs. These could be road signs, safety signs or signs you might find in the classroom. Keep them simple and easy to understand. Remember, these should be signs that they're familiar with already, they just need to put their meanings into English. They can use the given modal verbs to write sentences for each one. Students will have to get creative with their modal verbs to decide what they mean, and can work in pairs to write their own ideas. At the end, you can go over their answers together, and correct their grammar as you go along.

2. Agony Aunts- In order to practice using modal verbs for advice, your students can try their hands at being agony aunts. To open up the topic, tell your students that you have a problem you want them to help you with. This can be something as simple as “I’m hungry” or “I don’t know what to do this weekend.” Ask them to give you some advice. Once they do, work with them to flesh it out into a full sentence. You can do this by writing a gap fill on the board, such as

“You ____ go to a restaurant.”

Use this to elicit the following responses: Ought to; Should; Had better;

Then, students can practice giving advice with these words. You can either give them example problems to answer or have them write some of their own. The best choice for you will depend on the skill level of your class, as well as the amount of time you have. This could be a writing or conversation lesson, depending on how you structure it.

3. Fortune Tellers- Students can try predicting the future by role playing as fortune tellers. This is a great way to practice using “will,” “may” and “might.” There are two ways you can approach this topic. The first is to use palm reading. Busy Teacher has a great palm reading lesson plan. Combine this with One Stop English’s palm reading worksheet, and your students can learn what the lines on their hands mean. Then, they can use this knowledge to pair up, read their partner’s palm and use modal verbs to make predictions about their future. The second way to do it is by using tarot cards. Print out ISL Collective’s tarot cards for ESL classes, cut them up and give them out to students in pairs. Once your students have learned how to use the modal verbs, they can draw three cards at a time and use them to make predictions about their partners.

4. Guess the Job- Kick off this activity by having students brainstorm a list of jobs. Once they’ve done that, ask them to tell you the responsibilities of a

teacher. You can use their answers to teach them how to use the following modal verbs:

Have to

- Don't have to
- Needn't
- Mustn't

They can construct sentences like “you must take care of students,” “you don't have to wear a uniform” and “you mustn't be late for class.” After that, direct them back to the lists they made earlier and have them write similar sentences for the jobs they wrote down. In pairs, students can then discuss their own jobs using modal verbs. To wrap up, turn it into a guessing game. Ask each student to choose a job without telling their partner what it is. They can use modal verbs to describe the job and their partner can guess the job[4].

To sum up, it should be noted that covering many different uses of modal verbs in your class, be sure to have a lesson which combines them again. It makes sense to start with all the words you plan to cover in the first class and finish the same way. Since students have been focusing on just one use at a time, this lesson will bring to their attention the range of uses these words have and really challenge them. Fill in the blank and multiple choice worksheets may be appropriate and of course you can conduct role plays based on the different uses of modal verbs too.

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